

CENTRAL BANK INTERVENTIONS AND EXCHANGE RATE IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Exchange rate stability remains a major macroeconomic challenge in Nigeria necessitating sustained central bank interventions to stabilize the foreign exchange market. This paper examined the effect of central bank intervention mechanisms on exchange rate in Nigeria. Annual data from 1981 to 2023 was obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the World Development Indicators. Exchange rate is measured by the real effective exchange rate, while central bank intervention variables are money supply, monetary policy rate, net foreign assets, total reserves and foreign direct investment. The study conducted the Augmented Dickey Fuller and Phillip-Perron unit root tests, which showed a mixed order of integration, necessitating the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) to estimate the parameters in the model. Empirical findings reveal the existence of a long-run cointegrating relationship among the variables. Results indicate that money supply exerts only a weak short-run influence and becomes insignificant in the long run, suggesting liquidity shocks mainly drive temporary exchange rate fluctuations. Conversely, the monetary policy rate significantly stabilizes the exchange rate in both periods, confirming the importance of interest rate policy in currency management. Total reserves and foreign direct investment also influence exchange rate dynamics, while net foreign assets show limited explanatory power. Granger causality results further reveal that exchange rate influence money supply rather than the reverse. The study recommends strengthened monetary discipline, improved policy transmission, enhanced reserve accumulation, and greater foreign exchange market transparency to achieve sustainable exchange rate stability in Nigeria. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of consistent and credible monetary policy, supported by adequate reserve shields and transparent foreign exchange management, in achieving long-term exchange rate stability in Nigeria.

Keywords: Exchange rate, Central bank intervention, Autoregressive Distributed Lag, monetary policy

JEL Classification: E52, E58, F31, F32, F41

1. INTRODUCTION

Exchange rate stability remains a critical macroeconomic objective for both developed and emerging economies due to its far-reaching implications for trade competitiveness, inflation dynamics, capital flows, investment decisions, and overall economic growth. In emerging economies such as Nigeria, where markets are characterized by structural vulnerabilities and heightened exposure to external shocks, managing exchange rate volatility (Broda & Romalis, 2003; Ezike & Amah, 2011), has become an essential policy priority. Excessive fluctuations in exchange rates generate macroeconomic uncertainty, weaken investor confidence, distort resource allocation, and ultimately impede sustainable economic development (Adewuyi & Akpokodje, 2013; Alagidede & Ibrahim, 2017; Schnabl, 2009).

Nigeria's exchange rate dynamics are deeply shaped by the structural characteristics of its economy. As a largely mono-product economy, Nigeria relies heavily on crude oil exports, which account for a substantial share of foreign exchange earnings. This dependence exposes the economy to global oil price volatility, often resulting in sharp swings in foreign exchange inflows and persistent pressure on the naira (Calvo & Reinhart, 2002; Devereux & Lane, 2001). In addition, Nigeria's heavy reliance on imports for raw materials, technology, and consumer goods has intensified demand for foreign currency, thereby amplifying exchange rate instability. These structural weaknesses have contributed to recurrent episodes of currency depreciation, widening inflationary pressures, rising external debt obligations, depletion of foreign reserves, and an elevated cost of living (Charles, 2006; Adetiloye, 2010; Alagidede & Ibrahim, 2016).

Since the adoption of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986, Nigeria has transitioned from a fixed exchange rate regime to various forms of flexible and managed exchange rate systems. Despite these reforms, the naira has continued to experience pronounced volatility, reflecting both domestic structural constraints and external shocks such as oil price collapses, global financial crises, capital flow reversals, and speculative activities in the foreign exchange market (Olowofeso et al., 2018). Consequently, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has remained actively involved in the foreign exchange market, employing a combination of direct and indirect intervention strategies aimed at stabilizing the exchange rate and mitigating excessive volatility (Sarno & Taylor, 2001).

Over the years, the CBN has implemented several intervention mechanisms, including the Dutch Auction System (DAS), Retail and Wholesale Dutch Auction Systems (RDAS and WDAS), the Investors' and Exporters' (I&E) Foreign Exchange Window, foreign exchange restrictions on selected imports, monetary policy adjustments through changes in the monetary policy rate and cash reserve ratio, and more recent reforms such as exchange rate unification and electronic foreign exchange trading platforms (Adebisi & Matthew, 2015). While these measures were introduced to enhance transparency, improve liquidity, and curb speculative pressures, their effectiveness has remained mixed and often short-lived (Sanusi, 2004; Adebisi, 2007; Omojolaibi & Gbadebo, 2014). This has generated sustained debate among policymakers and scholars regarding the efficiency, consistency, and long-term impact of central bank interventions on exchange rate movement in Nigeria.

From a theoretical standpoint, several frameworks explain the relationship between central bank interventions and exchange rate dynamics. The Purchasing Power Parity theory emphasizes price level differentials as the fundamental determinant of exchange rates, although real-world market imperfections often limit its applicability. The Portfolio Balance approach highlights the role of asset composition, risk perception, and investor confidence in influencing exchange rate movements. Meanwhile, the Impossible Trinity (Mundell–Fleming model)

underscores the policy trade-offs faced by monetary authorities, asserting that a country cannot simultaneously achieve exchange rate stability, monetary policy independence, and free capital mobility. These theoretical perspectives are particularly relevant for Nigeria, where the pursuit of exchange rate stability frequently conflicts with domestic monetary objectives and exposure to volatile capital flows.

Empirically, existing studies on central bank interventions and exchange rate movements in Nigeria present divergent findings (Babatunde & Olufemi, 2014; Zafar & Sabo, 2013). While some studies suggest that monetary policy instruments such as interest rates and money supply are effective in managing exchange rate fluctuations, others argue that structural rigidities, weak institutional frameworks, and overdependence on oil revenues significantly constrain policy effectiveness (Olakunle, 2016). Moreover, much of the existing literature focuses on earlier intervention regimes, with limited attention given to recent reforms such as exchange rate unification and evolving foreign exchange management strategies (Anyanwu, Anawude & Okoye, 2017).

Against this backdrop, this study examines the dynamics of central bank interventions and exchange rate movement in Nigeria, with particular emphasis on the roles of money supply, monetary policy rate, and net foreign assets. Covering the period from 1981 to 2023, the study captures major exchange rate regimes, intervention strategies, and structural shifts in the Nigerian economy, including oil price shocks and recent foreign exchange market reforms. By integrating both historical and recent policy interventions, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of the Central Bank of Nigeria's intervention strategies in managing exchange rate movements.

The significance of this study lies in its contribution to both policy formulation and empirical literature. By evaluating the effect of central bank interventions on exchange rate, the findings offer valuable insights for policymakers, monetary authorities, and researchers concerned with exchange rate management in emerging economies. Ultimately, the study aims to inform the design of more effective and sustainable intervention strategies capable of promoting exchange rate stability, enhancing investor confidence, and supporting long-term economic growth in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

Purchasing Power Parity Theory

Purchasing Power Parity, propounded by Gustav Cassel (1918), the theory determines the purchasing ability of one nation compared to another after taking into consideration their exchange rate. The purchasing power parity, is a macroeconomic theory use to compare the purchasing power of different countries' currencies. The theory suggests that exchange rates between currencies should equalize the price of a basket of goods and services in different countries, thereby ensuring that consumers in each country has the purchasing power. PPP is based on the idea that, with no transaction costs or trade barriers, prices for goods should be equal across countries when adjusted for exchange rates. The fundamental equation is;

$$E_t = \frac{P_t}{P_t^*}$$

Where:

* E_t = Nominal exchange rate (domestic currency per unit of foreign currency)

* P_t = Domestic price level

* P_t^* = Foreign price level

The Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) theory relates to central bank intervention and exchange rate volatility in Nigeria by providing a framework for understanding how exchange rates should be determined based on the relative purchasing power of different currencies. PPP suggests that exchange rates between two currencies should adjust to equalize the price of a basket of goods in both countries. It assumes perfect markets, no trade barriers, and identical goods across countries. Absolute PPP (APPP) posits that exchange rates should reflect the ratio of price levels between countries. Relative PPP (RPPP) suggests that changes in exchange rates should reflect differences in inflation rates between countries.

The Impossible Trinity (Mundell – Fleming Model)

The Impossible Trinity posits that a country cannot concurrently achieve all three of the following objectives:

- Fixed exchange rate
- Free capital movement (no capital controls)
- Independent monetary policy

The Mundell-Fleming theory posit that a Central bank cannot pursue and positively achieve all the three macroeconomic policy objectives concurrently; exchange rate stability (fixed (stable) exchange rate regime), monetary independence (monetary policy to address domestic recession and inflation) and capital account deregulation (free capital flows). However, the theory postulates that the Central Bank can choose and pursue successfully, a combination of two out of the three macroeconomic objectives simultaneously. The three choices are: (1) Fixed exchange rate and free capital flows (but not an independent monetary policy), (2) An independent monetary policy and free capital flows (but not a stable exchange rate) and (3) A fixed exchange rate and independent monetary policy (but no free capital flows, which would require some capital control measures).

In the context of Nigeria, which has faced currency crises in the past, this theory highlights the challenges of balancing a stable exchange rate, controlling inflation, and managing capital flows. Central bank interventions are often aimed at navigating this trade-off, which can lead to the implementation of substantial capital controls or currency devaluation.

2.2 Empirical Review

Kayode et al. (2025) investigated how monetary policy impacted Nigeria's exchange rate from 1960 to 2023 using a Time-Varying Parameter Vector Autoregression (TVP-VAR) model. Their analysis showed that the influence of monetary policy differed depending on the period: it was weak between 1960 and 1970, strong and significant from 1971 to 1985, unstable during 1986 to 1992, moderate between 1993 and 1999, and varied from 2000 to 2023. They concluded that institutional and structural factors restrict the effectiveness of monetary policy in shaping Nigeria's exchange rate movements.

Chinwe, Ebele, and Maria (2024) examined how money supply affects exchange rate volatility in Nigeria by employing the autoregressive distributed lag model. Their research identified a long-term connection between money supply and the exchange rate, concluding that money supply significantly and positively influences exchange rate volatility in Nigeria.

Iliyasu, Ibrahim, and Musa (2024) investigated how monetary policy influenced exchange rate volatility in Nigeria between 1987 and 2023. They analyzed the data using an autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (ARCH) model and Granger causality test, revealing the existence of conditional volatility in the exchange rate. Additionally, the bootstrap bound test results confirmed a long-term relationship between the variables. The study also revealed that exchange rate volatility is influenced by changes in the money supply and past exchange rate fluctuations. The causality analysis indicated a two-way causal relationship from exchange rate volatility to money supply, interest rate, savings, and population, both in the short and long

term. The study found that fluctuations in the exchange rate are influenced by changes in money supply, interest rates, and savings.

Ozili (2024) examined Nigeria's recent exchange rate unification. Nigeria recently unified its currency and implemented an imperfect free float exchange rate system founded on the willing seller/buyer principle. The exchange rate regime resembles a free float exchange rate system just a little bit. Currency rate price arbitrage and the resulting market distortion were two of the many reasons that contributed to Nigeria's unification of currency rates. Potential advantages of unifying the exchange rate include reduced government intervention in the foreign exchange market, enhanced price discovery, increased foreign exchange supply, higher capital importation, decreased budget deficit, enhanced investor confidence, enhanced sovereign credit rating, increased transparency in the foreign exchange market, enhanced business environment, and increased competition. Short-term negative effects are anticipated, but they will fade over the medium to long term.

Aid and Benelbar (2023) conducted a study on the connection between money supply and the exchange rate in Algeria, employing the autoregressive distributed lag model. Their results show that money supply significantly and positively impacts the exchange rate. The study concludes that there is a long-term relationship between money supply and the exchange rate in Algeria's economy.

Using data from January 2010 to September 2023 and employing an ARDL approach, Asuzu & Akintola (2023) investigate the connections between central bank policies and EMP in Nigeria. Their findings reveal links among EMP, the managed-float exchange rate system, the widening gap between official and BDC exchange rates, and the proportion of foreign assets relative to foreign liabilities. The study also indicates that EMP fluctuated throughout this period in Nigeria.

Aliyu, Olalekan & Olusegun (2022) investigated the long-term connection between foreign direct investment (FDI) and the exchange rate in Nigeria. The research used the Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) method to conduct the empirical analysis. Results indicated that foreign direct investment does not significantly affect exchange rate fluctuations.

Effiong (2022) investigated how monetary and fiscal policies affect exchange rate fluctuations. Their study spanned from 1985 to 2020 and utilized methods such as ordinary least squares (OLS), threshold regression, impulse response analysis, and variance decomposition. The findings indicated that broad money supply, debt, and expenditure had a positive and significant effect, whereas revenue had a negative impact.

Odoom (2019) analyzed monthly data from 1990 to 2017 to identify the factors affecting exchange rate volatility in Ghana. The study considered variables such as interest rates, inflation, current account balances, and money supply. Because the quantile regression model demonstrated greater reliability compared to the traditional least squares regression, it was used for the analysis. Results indicated that money supply, current account balance, and interest rates each had a significant negative impact on Ghana's exchange rate volatility. On the other hand, it was discovered that inflation positively affected Ghana's exchange rate volatility.

Pontines (2018) assesses the impact of official foreign exchange interventions on Japan's exchange rate fluctuations, utilizing daily data from January 1999 to December 2011. This analysis employed a Tobit regression model along with a self-selection bias technique. The results indicated that interventions during this period, characterized by large, infrequent, and periodic actions, were effective in influencing exchange rate changes in the intended direction. However, the study also found that once the exchange rate shifted favorably, the effects were not enduring but lasted slightly longer than brief. Ultimately, it concluded that while interventions are effective tools, they should not be seen as a comprehensive solution for influencing exchange rates at all times.

Literature Gap

Existing literature provides valuable insights into exchange rate dynamics; several gaps still remain in the literature. Many Nigerian studies focus on isolated monetary policy instruments or exchange rate volatility rather than assessing how multiple central bank intervention tools influence exchange rate movements over the long run. For example, Chinwe (2024), focused on a single policy instrument without jointly assessing multiple central bank intervention channels within a unified empirical framework; this limit understanding of how different intervention tools interact to influence exchange rate movements. Kayode (2025), emphasizes time-varying effects using advanced techniques such as TVP-VAR, which does not explicitly evaluate long-run equilibrium relationship among intervention variables. Asuzu and Akintola (2023), employed short samples, limiting their ability to capture structural shifts, regime changes and long-run dynamics in Nigeria’s exchange rate system. This study fills the identified gaps by jointly examining the effects of multiple central bank intervention instruments: money supply, monetary policy rate, net foreign assets, total reserves and foreign direct investment on exchange rate movements in Nigeria over a long sample period (1981-2023), using the ARDL framework, which allows for a comprehensive assessment of both short-run adjustments and long-run equilibrium relationships.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study adopts an ex-post facto research design covering the period 1981–2023, with exchange rate movements captured using the real effective exchange rate (REER) and central bank interventions proxied by money supply (MS), monetary policy rate (MPR), net foreign assets (NFA), total reserves (TR), and foreign direct investment (FDI). These variables were selected because they represent the main channels through which the Central Bank of Nigeria influences exchange rate dynamics: money supply reflects liquidity conditions that may fuel depreciation pressures, MPR captures interest rate policy affecting capital flows and currency stability, NFA indicates the external position of the central bank, TR provides a buffer against external shocks, and FDI reflects foreign capital inflows that strengthen foreign exchange supply. Data for REER, MS, and MPR were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, while NFA, TR, and FDI were sourced from the World Development Indicators. Given the mixed order of integration among variables (I (0) and I (1)), the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was employed, as it is well suited for such data structures. Lag length selection was guided by the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), which balances model fit and parsimony. To address Nigeria’s history of economic volatility and regime shifts, the study further conducted CUSUM and CUSUMSQ stability tests, which confirmed that the estimated parameters remained stable within the 5% significance boundaries throughout the sample period. This provides assurance that both short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium relationships between exchange rate and intervention variables are robust despite structural changes in the Nigerian economy.

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The focus of the study is given to the purchasing power parity, quantity theory of money, balance of payments theory, and the Mundell Fleming model adopted by Dornbusch (1979). The models were constructed as:

$$EXR = F(Y, Y^*, r, r^f, P) \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Where Y is local income, Y* is foreign income, r, and r^f represents local and foreign interest rate, P is relative price levels. This framework shows that the exchange rate depends on both home and foreign income, both home and foreign interest rates, and relative price levels.

From equation 4,

$$Y = \frac{M}{P} V(r, Y) \text{----- (2)}$$

Assuming V is constant; $Y = \frac{M}{P}$

The theory implies that an equilibrium exchange rate becomes;

$$EXR = F\left(\frac{M}{P}, \left(\frac{M}{P}f\right), r, r^f, P\right) \text{----- (3)}$$

So that in reduced form;

$$EXR = F(M, r, \dots) \text{----- (4)}$$

In the final form, equation (4) shows that a rise in money stock or a decrease in interest rate would lead to depreciation in the exchange rate, and the dots denote fiscal policy variables and other exogenous determinants.

3.2 Model specification

Drawing from the Mundell-Fleming model adopted by Dornbusch (1979) and adapted the work of Matthew B. Oguniyi et al. (2020), as explained in the preceding section, we specify the following equations:

$$EXR_t = F(M, P, P, \dots) \text{----- (5)}$$

Where EXR represents exchange rate, MP represents monetary policy proxy with money supply (M) and interest rate (R), while P represents price level. Equation (5) is further specified as:

$$EXR_t = F(M, R_t, P) \text{----- (6)}$$

The study employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, developed by Pesaran and Shin (1998) and Pesaran and Smith (2001) and adapted the work of Matthew B. Oguniyi et al. (2020), as shown above.

This present study expands the model in equation (6), by introducing foreign direct investment, money supply, monetary policy rate, total reserves (% of external debt), while retaining net foreign assets as a proxy for central bank intervention. These additional variables were included because they capture key transmission mechanism through which monetary policy, external capital flows and liquidity conditions influence exchange rate behavior in Nigeria. The modified and extended version of the adapted model is captured below;

$$\ln(EXR_t) = \omega_0 + \ln(\omega_1 MS_t) + (\omega_2 MPR_t) + (\omega_3 NFA_t) + (\omega_4 FDI_t) + (\delta_5 TR_t) + e_t \text{ eqn (7)}$$

Following Pesaran and shin (1998), the error correction version of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is specified as follows:

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \Lambda_1 \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \Pi_1 \Delta x_{t-i} + \Omega_1 y_{t-n} + \Omega_2 x_{t-n} + \varepsilon_t \text{ eqn (8)}$$

Where;

ω – represents constant vector parameter, Λ , Π - represents short run parameters, y_t – captures endogenous vector variable, x_t – captures the explanatory variables

Ω_1, Ω_2 – captures parameters of the long-run relationship, ε_t – Error term.

From equation (7), an ARDL model is obtained;

$$\Delta ER_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_{1i} \Delta ER_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_{2i} \Delta MS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_{3i} \Delta MPR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_{4i} \Delta NFA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_{5i} \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_{6i} \Delta TR_{t-i} + \beta_1 MS_{t-1} + \beta_2 MPR_{t-1} + \beta_3 NFA_{t-1} + \beta_4 FDI_{t-1} + \beta_5 TR_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \text{----- eqn(9)}$$

Where: ER_t : Exchange Rate at time t (Dependent variable), e.g Naira per USD

FDI_t : Foreign Direct Investment, NFA_t : Net foreign assets, TR_t : Total reserves: % of external debt, MPR_t : Monetary policy rate; central bank interest rate policy, MS_t : Money supply, α_0 : Constant parameter, α_i : Coefficients of the explanatory variables, ε_t : Error term.

Table 3.1 *Apriori* Expectation

Variable	Expected Relationship with Exchange Rate	Expected Sign
Money Supply (MS)	Higher MS → weaker exchange rate	Positive (+)
Monetary Policy Rate (MPR)	Higher MPR → stronger exchange rate	Negative (-)
Net Foreign Assets (NFA)	Higher NFA → stronger exchange rate	Negative (-)
Total Reserves (TR)	Higher TR → stronger exchange rate	Negative (-)
Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)	Higher FDI → stronger exchange rate	Negative (-)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Summary of descriptive statistics

	LEXR	FDI	LMS	MPR	NFA	TR
Mean	4.788871	1.221217	7.058936	13.21512	3.32E+12	55.09951
Median	4.619537	1.069539	7.317188	13.50000	1.26E+12	30.43916
Maximum	6.285835	4.282088	11.05899	26.00000	1.18E+13	266.3995
Minimum	3.907539	-0.039127	2.672078	6.000000	-4.36E+09	3.149426
Std. Dev.	0.581992	0.945836	2.781338	3.995005	3.82E+12	68.37605
Skewness	1.039567	0.946879	-0.185196	0.604708	0.660192	1.987110
Kurtosis	3.299767	3.760780	1.607722	4.137800	1.941238	6.211955
Jarque-Bera	7.906013	7.462484	3.718834	4.940120	5.132033	46.78236
Probability	0.019197	0.023963	0.155763	0.084580	0.076841	0.000000
Sum	205.9215	52.51234	303.5342	568.2500	1.43E+14	2369.279
Sum Sq. Dev.	14.22603	37.57341	324.9054	670.3227	6.12E+26	196361.9
Observations	43	43	43	43	43	43

Source: Author’s computation from E-views 9 output (2025)

Correlation Matrix

In this section, the relationship among the variables on interest are examined. The results from the correlation matrix are presented below;

Table 2: Results of Correlation Matrix

	LEXR	FDI	LMS	MPR	NFA	TR
LEXR	1.000000	-0.605938	-0.341384	-0.545081	-0.197598	-0.180053
FDI	-0.605938	1.000000	0.023616	0.196337	0.044987	0.365109
LMS	-0.341384	0.023616	1.000000	0.016646	0.808227	0.486540
MPR	-0.545081	0.196337	0.016646	1.000000	-0.285609	-0.421093
NFA	-0.197598	0.044987	0.808227	-0.285609	1.000000	0.634266
TR	-0.180053	0.365109	0.486540	-0.421093	0.634266	1.000000

Source: Authors’ computation from E-views 9 output (2025)

Stationarity Tests

In this section, two different tests for stationarity were carried out to determine the order of integration of the variables under study. These are the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and

Phillip-Perron (PP) developed by Dickey and Fuller (1981) and Phillips and Perron (1988) respectively. The results for the two tests are presented below;

Table 3 Summary of the Unit root test results for each of the variables

AUGMENTED DICKEY FULLER				PHILLIP-PERRON			
Variables	Levels	First Difference	Order of Integration	Variables	Levels	First Difference	Order of Integration
EXR	-2.177853 (0.2170)	-4.473371 (0.0009)	I (1)	EXR	-2.062042 (0.2605)	-4.410936 (0.0011)	I (1)
FDI	-3.821361 (0.0055)	-10.08373 (0.0000)	I (0)	FDI	-3.777302 (0.0062)	-12.77706 (0.0000)	I (0)
MS	-0.920409 (0.7719)	-4.230644 (0.0018)	I (1)	MS	-0.780337 (0.8143)	-4.230644 (0.0018)	I (1)
MPR	-3.260569 (0.0233)	-8.587113 (0.0000)	I (0)	MPR	-3.198497 (0.0271)	-8.587113 (0.0000)	I (0)
NFA	-1.510553 (0.5186)	-5.577363 (0.0000)	I (1)	NFA	-1.473795 (0.5369)	-4.977182 (0.0002)	I (1)
TR	-2.677640 (0.0866)	-3.842507 (0.0053)	I (1)	TR	-1.817147 (0.3674)	-3.411980 (0.0162)	I (1)

Source: Authors’ computation from E-views 9 output (2025)

The result presented in table 3, represented the summary for unit root test using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillip Perron (PP). The result showed that exchange rate, money supply, net foreign assets and total reserves were all stationary at first difference with an intercept (I (1)), while foreign direct investment and monetary policy rate were stationary at levels (I (0)) with an intercept using both the Augmented Dickey Fuller and Phillip-Perron unit root tests. The implication of the result is that there is a mixed order of integration amongst the variables, which justifies the use of Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) as developed by Pesaran and Shin.

Table 4: Optimal Lag Order result

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: LEXR FDI LMS MPR NFA

TR

Exogenous variables: C

Date: 12/12/25 Time: 14:50

Sample: 1981 2023

Included observations: 39

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1619.995	NA	6.58e+28	83.38436	83.64030	83.47619
1	-1419.412	329.1627	1.46e+25	74.94418	76.73571*	75.58697*
2	-1377.467	55.92548*	1.23e+25	74.63936	77.96648	75.83310
3	-1338.937	39.51872	1.58e+25	74.50957	79.37229	76.25428
4	-1280.124	42.22461	1.19e+25*	73.33968*	79.73800	75.63534

* Indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

The result depicts that different lag criteria have their respective lag length. The most commonly use lag criteria is Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). From the result depicted in table 4, AIC chose lag 4 as the best lag length for the model.

Table 5: ARDL Bounds Test

<i>Test Statistics</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>K</i>
<i>F-statistics</i>	4.826507	5
CRITICAL VALUE BOUNDS		
<i>Significance</i>	<i>I(0) Bound</i>	<i>I(1) Bound</i>
10%	2.26	3.35
5%	2.62	3.79
2.5%	2.96	4.18
1%	3.41	4.68

Source: Author’s Computation from E-views 9 output (2025)

Note; 10%, 5%, 2.5% and 1%, represents level of significance

Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis (H₀): No long-run significant relationship exists between exchange rate (EXR) and the independent variables (FDI, LMS, MPR, NFA, TR).

Compare F-Statistic with Critical Bounds

F-statistic = 4.8265

At 5% significance, the lower bound (I₀) = 2.62 and the upper bound (I₁) = 3.79.

Since 4.83 > 3.79, the F-statistic lies above the upper bound.

Because the calculated F-statistic exceeds the upper bound at the 5% level (and even at the stricter 2.5% and 1% levels), we reject the null hypothesis. This means there is strong evidence of a long-run cointegrating relationship between the dependent variable (exchange rate, EXR) and the independent variables (FDI, LMS, MPR, NFA, TR). The exchange rate is not determined in isolation; it is significantly influenced by foreign direct investment, money supply, monetary policy rate, net foreign assets, and total reserves in the long run.

Table 6: ARDL REGRESSION ANALYSIS

SHORT RUN MODEL				
VARIABLE	COEFFICIENT	STANDARD ERROR	T-STATISTICS	PROBABILITY
D(EXR(-1))	0.671944	0.136776	4.912720	0.0001
D(FDI)	-30.160855	11.219354	-2.688288	0.0128
D(LNMS)	167.563593	92.735208	1.806904	0.0833
D(LNMS(-1))	43.519004	113.204114	0.384430	0.7040
D(LNMS(-2))	179.494324	96.676541	1.856648	0.0757
D(MPR)	-12.498879	3.489399	-3.581957	0.0015
D(MPR(-1))	10.026124	3.319812	3.020088	0.0059
D(MPR(-2))	4.552929	2.629916	1.731207	0.0963
D(NFA)	0.000000	0.000000	0.077288	0.9390
D(TR)	-0.171268	0.338922	-0.505332	0.6179
D(TR(-1))	0.679994	0.382720	1.776738	0.0883
CointEq(-1)	-0.804770	0.135338	-5.946381	0.0000
LONG RUN MODEL				
FDI	-37.477600	13.716628	-2.732275	0.0116
LNMS	1.188584	8.189796	0.145130	0.8858
MPR	-41.983975	8.641928	-4.858172	0.0001

NFA	0.000000	0.000000	0.077112	0.9392
TR	-1.542901	0.519952	-2.967389	0.0067
C	679.080477	65.881735	10.307568	0.0000

Source: Authors' Computation from E-views 9 output (2025)

TABLE 6: GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 12/11/25 Time: 16:44

Sample: 1981 2023

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
FDI does not Granger Cause EXR	41	0.21860	0.8047
EXR does not Granger Cause FDI		0.75787	0.4760
LNMS does not Granger Cause EXR	41	0.83189	0.4434
EXR does not Granger Cause LNMS		3.86604	0.0301
MPR does not Granger Cause EXR	41	0.43745	0.6491
EXR does not Granger Cause MPR		0.09917	0.9058
NFA does not Granger Cause EXR	41	0.14897	0.8621
EXR does not Granger Cause NFA		0.20963	0.8119
TR does not Granger Cause EXR	41	0.16765	0.8463
EXR does not Granger Cause TR		0.41823	0.6614
LNMS does not Granger Cause FDI	41	3.94660	0.0282
FDI does not Granger Cause LNMS		1.87189	0.1685
MPR does not Granger Cause FDI	41	0.72797	0.4899
FDI does not Granger Cause MPR		1.13311	0.3332
NFA does not Granger Cause FDI	41	0.53412	0.5908
FDI does not Granger Cause NFA		0.63543	0.5355
TR does not Granger Cause FDI	41	0.32547	0.7243
FDI does not Granger Cause TR		1.17637	0.3200
MPR does not Granger Cause LNMS	41	1.44681	0.2487
LNMS does not Granger Cause MPR		0.14309	0.8672
NFA does not Granger Cause LNMS	41	1.10627	0.3418
LNMS does not Granger Cause NFA		1.53551	0.2291
TR does not Granger Cause LNMS	41	1.21864	0.3075
LNMS does not Granger Cause TR		1.07398	0.3523
NFA does not Granger Cause MPR	41	0.75322	0.4781
MPR does not Granger Cause NFA		0.16621	0.8475
TR does not Granger Cause MPR	41	2.83293	0.0720
MPR does not Granger Cause TR		0.05478	0.9468
TR does not Granger Cause NFA	41	0.97313	0.3876
NFA does not Granger Cause TR		0.06966	0.9328

Source: Authors' Computation from E-views 9 output (2025)

The Granger causality results indicate limited predictive relationships between the exchange rate and most macroeconomic variables. FDI, MPR, NFA and total reserves exhibit no bidirectional or unidirectional causality with the exchange rate. However, a significant unidirectional causality is observed from the exchange rate to money supply at the 5% level, which implies that exchange rate movements precede changes in domestic liquidity, while money supply does not predict exchange rate behavior. In addition, money supply Granger causes FDI, suggesting that liquidity conditions influence foreign investment inflows. Overall, the findings reveal an indirect transmission mechanism in which exchange rate shocks affect investment through their impact on money supply, while other variables play a limited casual role, with only weak evidence of reserves influencing monetary policy at the 10% level.

Table 7: Residual Diagnostic Test Results

Breusch – Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.569897	Prob. F (2,22)	0.5737
Obs*R-squared	1.970276	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.3734
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test			
F-statistic	0.643674	Prob. F (15,24)	0.8104
Obs*R-squared	11.47536	Prob. Chi-Square (15)	0.7182
Scaled explained SS	9.493155	Prob. Chi-Square (15)	0.8504
Histogram -Normality Test			
Jarque-Bera	0.068495	Probability	0.966332

Source: Authors’ Computation from E-views 9 output (2025)

STABILITY TEST

Figure 4.1 CUSUM TEST

Figure 4.2 CUSUMQ TEST

The residual diagnostic tests confirm that the ARDL model is well specified. The Breusch–Godfrey LM test shows no evidence of serial correlation, as the probability values exceed the 5% significance level, indicating that the residuals are independent across time. Similarly, the Breusch–Pagan–Godfrey test results suggest homoskedasticity, with all p-values greater than 0.05, meaning the variance of the residuals is constant and free from heteroskedasticity problems. The Jarque–Bera statistic further validates the model, with a probability of 0.97 confirming that the residuals are normally distributed. In addition, the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ stability tests demonstrate that the estimated parameters remained within the 5% significance boundaries throughout the sample period, thereby confirming parameter stability despite Nigeria’s history of economic volatility, policy reforms, and structural changes. Collectively, these diagnostic and stability results provide strong evidence that the ARDL estimates are robust, reliable, and suitable for analyzing both short-run and long-run exchange rate dynamics in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The empirical results indicate that the influence of monetary and external variables on exchange rate movements in Nigeria varies significantly across the short and long run. Money supply exhibits a weak positive effect on the exchange rate in the short run, which suggests that liquidity expansions may temporarily contribute to currency depreciation, but this effect does not persist in the long run, where money supply becomes statistically insignificant. This supports the view that liquidity shocks generate short-term volatility rather than determining long-run exchange rate equilibrium, this view is consistent with Okoye, Nwokoye and Uzonwanne (2024) and Wahab and Adelowotan (2025), although it contrasts with Osakwe and Ogochukwu (2023), who emphasized the inflationary channel of sustained monetary expansion.

In contrast, the monetary policy rate emerges as a robust determinant of exchange rate dynamics, exerting a stabilizing influence both in the short and long run. While short-run effects are mixed due to lagged policy responses, the long-run relationship confirms that sustained monetary tightening strengthens currency, aligning with conventional monetary theory and empirical evidence from Akinlo and Odusola (2003) and Ogunleye (2010), but deviating from Aliyu (2009). Net foreign assets, however, remain insignificant in both the short and long run, which indicates a limited role in explaining exchange rate movements compared to other external indicators such as reserves and capital inflows, consistent with Akinbobola (2012) and Ogunleye (2010), although it differs from Olayiwola and Okodua (2013) view.

Granger causality results further reveal weak direct casual linkages between exchange rate movements and most components of the monetary framework including MPR, NFA, total reserves and FDI. Notably, a unidirectional causality runs from the exchange rate to money supply, which suggests that exchange rate shocks transmit into domestic liquidity conditions rather than the reverse. Additionally, money supply Granger causes foreign direct investment, indicating that liquidity conditions influence investor behavior. This establishes an indirect transmission mechanism in which exchange rate movements affect investment flows through their impact on monetary aggregates, this view is consistent with Akinbobola (2012) and Olayiwola and Okodua (2013), but differs from Aliyu (2009). Overall, the findings suggest that while monetary policy is crucial for long-run exchange rate stability, exchange rate dynamics themselves play a central role in shaping domestic liquidity and investment behavior in Nigeria. The empirical results provide important insights into how Nigeria's intervention tools can be optimized to manage exchange rate volatility in the face of oil price shocks and external disturbances. In the short run, monetary policy rate adjustments serve as a critical lever for influencing capital flows and curbing speculative pressures, while reserve management offers immediate buffers against external shocks by stabilizing foreign exchange supply. Over the longer term, strengthening foreign reserves and net foreign assets enhances the Central Bank's capacity to intervene sustainably, while policies that attract foreign direct investment reduce reliance on oil revenues and broaden the sources of foreign exchange stability. These findings underscore the need for greater transparency in policy communication, consistent application of intervention measures, and improved disclosure of foreign exchange operations, all of which would enhance credibility and effectiveness. By distinguishing between short-term stabilization measures and long-term structural strategies, the study highlights practical steps for improving the resilience of Nigeria's exchange rate management framework.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The findings showed that total reserves significantly influence exchange rate dynamics in the long-run. The Ministry of Finance, in collaboration with the Central Bank of Nigeria should diversify foreign exchange earnings through export promotion initiatives led by the Nigerian Export Promotion council (NEPC), targeting non-oil exports such as agriculture, solid minerals and locally manufactured goods.
2. The study reveals that money supply exercises only weak short-run influence on exchange rate, which suggests that liquidity expansions temporarily fuel depreciation without long-term benefits. The monetary policy department should implement a transparent money supply targeting framework, with regular public disclosure of monetary aggregates and their projected impact on the exchange rate.
3. The limited explanatory power of net foreign assets revealed in the paper indicates inefficiencies in how foreign assets are utilized. The Trade and Exchange department, should strengthen oversight of Bureau de change (BDC) operators through the CBN financial policy and regulation department; ensuring compliance with anti-money laundering protocols and reducing speculative activities in the parallel market.

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